

A model-based 2D to 3D glioma MRI synthesis from healthy samples

Author

Yannuo Wen – School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University College Dublin, D04 V1W8, Dublin, Ireland

Kathleen M. Curran – School of Medicine, University College Dublin, D04 V1W8, Dublin, Ireland

John J. Healy – School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University College Dublin, D04 V1W8, Dublin, Ireland

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Abstract

In the application of deep learning models in medical imaging, high-quality real datasets are usually extremely scarce and expensive. Although image synthesis schemes such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) are widely used in 2D synthesis, there is a lack of 3D synthetic models or mature schemes for moving from 2D slices to 3D models. This further limits the development of deep models for 3D medical imaging, which has already demonstrated superiority. To synthesize high-quality realistic 3D medical images, we propose a 3D model-based synthesis method to synthesize samples with lesions using healthy samples. The method utilizes a healthy dataset and a lesion-containing dataset with

labels (e.g. segmentation masks). It generates a computer-rendered 3D model from each healthy and lesioned sample, combines and reconstructs a lesioned 3D image using automatic adaptation. The synthetic 3D image will be resliced, and a fine-tuned 2D-LDM will be used to reconstruct every 2D slice. Their corresponding segmentation masks will be obtained during the synthesis procedure. We apply this method to the task of automatic segmentation of glioma MRI, augment the glioma MRI dataset with synthetic image, and train the 3D-nnUnet to evaluate the synthesis quality. Results show that 3D-nnUnet trained on the augmented data can enhance the Dice coefficient (DSC) by a factor of 0.163 on ultra-small datasets. The proposed method has potential in the field of rare diseases, bringing feasibility for deep learning modeling under data scarcity.

Introduction and Related Works

Synthesis of three-dimensional (3D) images and models, driven by advances in deep generative modeling, has become a key area in computer vision and medical imaging [1]. However, compared to 2D image synthesis, 3D image synthesis is still in a relatively primitive stage due to limitations such as the huge amount of computation and the difficulty of training the 3D synthesis model itself [2].

2D and 3D Image Synthesis 2D image synthesis has been able to generate realistic images, where Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) have achieved remarkable results in this field [3,4]. 2D image synthesis can be applied to data augmentation to address the challenge of data scarcity; to transform images from one modality to another (e.g., generating synthetic CT images from MRI scans); or to aid in the creation of datasets with the patient's privacy features removed.

Regarding the task of 3D medical image processing, depth models based on 3D images usually have higher accuracy due to the ability to utilize

information in more dimensions, e.g., 3D-nnUnet [5]. Therefore, 3D medical image synthesis has good prospects for assisting the training of 3D depth models. Hu et al. [6] proposed an unsupervised domain adaptation strategy based on pre-trained VAEs to enhance the generalization ability of the synthesized models. Khader et al. [7] proposed a 3D denoising diffusion probabilistic model, which is capable of generating high-resolution MRI scans with better performance than 3D-GAN.

Existing Problems and Proposed Solutions Despite some advances in 3D medical image synthesis techniques, the problems of high computational complexity and low result confidence are difficult to be solved [8]. To address these problems, we propose a synthesis method from 2D slices to 3D images based on contour model guided adaptation. The brain tissue and corresponding contour model are rendered and normalized. Then, a real tumor MRI is separated by the segmentation mask provided by the lesioned dataset and embedded into the healthy brain after adaptive position adjustment. The image covered by the tumor is reconstructed by LDM to obtain a high quality MRI image containing the lesion.

Materials and Proposed Methods

Datasets and Pre-processing To better investigate the proposed methods, two public dataset is used for training and evaluation. Skull-stripped healthy brain MRI from the NFBS dataset [9] and WHO Grade 4 glioma MRI from the UCSF-PDGM dataset [10] are used for training and evaluation. For glioma MRI, all but the tumor site was removed using the provided segmentation mask. The resolution of the xxy axis of each slice is uniformly normalized to 192×192.

Model-based Approach With the normalized healthy brain and glioma only MRI, the proposed workflow design and illustration is shown in Figure 1. After the workflow, reconstructed MRI slices will combined and present a full 3D synthetic MRI with glioma.

Results and Conclusion

We apply our proposed method to a subset of the UCSF-PDGM dataset, containing only 48 MRIs, in which 32 MRIs are used to fine-tune the LDM, rendering the contour model, and train the barrier adaptation. 128 synthetic 3D MRIs are generated out of the 32 MRIs, 160 MRIs in total used to train the 3D-nnUNet, and test on the other 16 MRIs. Result shows in Table 1, where the test result is given by Dice Score.

The results demonstrate that the images generated by our proposed method are close to the real data in terms of quality and its proximity to the real data. In the case of extremely scarce data, synthesized 3D MRIs can substantially improve the training results. This provides the feasibility of deep model training for rare and privacy highly relevant diseases.

In future work, further segmented 3D modeling is worth exploring, such as modeling of multi-channel tumor segmentation masks and multi-partitioned brain tissue modeling. Fully synthetic solutions will also be a focus of

TABLE 1: Segmentation model training result for different sample size

Training Data	3D nnUNet Test Result
32 MRI Samples	0.7039
32 MRI Samples + 128 Synthetic Samples	0.8185
32 MRI Samples + 128 Extra Real MRIs	0.8204

research to move away from the reliance on healthy MRI data. Generalization of such synthesis methods to other diseases, as well as to other types of 3D medical images, such as CT, will also be directions worth investigating.

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